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Determination of hydraulic parameters by periodic
pumping tests on perforated rock samples
(Report)

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Abstract

We investigated the applicability of oscillatory pore-fluid tests for the characterization of perforated rock samples in the laboratory is investigated. Wellbore perforations, penetrating casing and cementation, are performed to enable connection to hydrocarbon reservoirs. The central objective of this work was to determine the hydraulic parameters of the crushed zone, the damaged rock volume surrounding the perforation shot, and identifying potential issues related to experimental setup and data evaluation. For the data analysis, an analytical model was developed and complemented by a numerical simulation. Comparing the model to laboratory data allows the calculation of hydraulic properties.

The numerical simulation revealed only small deviations from the analytical model, hence providing an affirmation of concept. However, the laboratory data deviate from the predictions of the model. The examination of possible sources of error demonstrated the sensitivity of flow measurements possible influences by the supply line and potential unknown hydraulic elements. The precise characterization of the entire volume connecting excitation pump and rock sample is crucial for the determination of hydraulic properties of the crushed zone.

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1. Introduction

In the issue of fluid flow through the subsurface, the hydraulic parameters constitute the relevant information needed to characterize the ability of a rock to store or transport a fluid. Thus, the determination of these rock properties is crucial for applications related to exploitation of hydrocarbons or geothermal energy. An investigation in laboratory experiments is desirable as the productivity of wells is influenced by different complex factors like reservoir connection, formation, fluid and tubing characteristic (Grove et al., 2011). When drilling for hydrocarbons, the installation of a casing and cementation is usually indispensable, leading to difficulties in connecting reservoir and borehole.

The company DynaEnergetics GmbH & Co. KG, Troisdorf, Germany develops and produces these well completion systems providing solutions for perforation with shaped charges. Piercing the casing and cementation, the perforation tunnel also increases the effective wellbore radius and overcomes the area damaged by the drilling process. Despite all advantages, the perforation has an influence on the bedrock characteristics and produces a crushed zone formed as a skin around the tunnel. This crushed zone is assumed to have lower transport properties (Papamichos et al., 1993).

Conventional investigations of hydraulic rock properties applying pumping tests use a stimulation signal in pressure and flow to draw conclusions from characteristics of normalization of pressure signal (e.g. Horne, 1992; Matthews and Russel, 1967; Fetter, 2001). Periodic pumping tests provide information on hydraulic properties complementary to conventional methods (Rasmussen et al., 2003; Renner and Messar, 2006). Periodic pumping tests are advantageous over conventional methods in various domains. The oscillation can be superposed on any transient signal since the excitation signal is detected by a Fast Fourier Transform. Therefore, small pressure amplitudes are applicable, avoiding non-Darcian effects. In addition, the variation of applied frequency and amplitude opens the possibility of different exploration objectives without a change of setup and long observation periods (Black and Kipp, 1981; Hollaender and Gringarten, 2002; Renner and Messar, 2006; Bahkos et al., 2014; Cardiff and Sayler, 2016).

Purpose of the performed laboratory study is to constrain the hydraulic parameters of the crushed zone with oscillatory pore-pressure tests with focus on using the pore-flow method introduced by Song and Renner (2007). Supporting insights can be received with the pore-pressure method. The oscillation tests were performed on perforated and drilled rock samples at the laboratory of DynaEnergetics, located in Troisdorf, Germany. Samples are placed between an upstream and a downstream reservoir whereas the upstream pressure is oscillated. Comparing the signals from the different reservoirs, the phase shift and amplitude ratio are the characterizing data which is then compared to analytic solutions of the diffusion equation. The analytical models were calculated taking geometry and boundary conditions into account,

allowing to determine hydraulic properties for the crushed zone. As the penetration depth is dependent on the diffusivity and oscillation frequency, high frequencies were applied to obtain small penetration depth to minimize the influence of undestroyed rock in the data. To complement the laboratory measurements, numerical modelling using COMSOL Multiphysics was performed. The diffusion equation was solved numerically for a simplified geometry with boundary conditions, similar to the analytical model. The source was defined analogous to the laboratory measurements. Hence, the possibility to review the experimentally obtained data and determined properties is created. Furthermore, the numerical work enables a parameter study allowing an investigation of sensitivity towards small changes in geometry and a comparison to the prediction of analytical model.

Figure 1.1: Graphical illustration of a perforation short piercing the casing and damaged zone around the borehole enabling the connection to the undestroyed rock (from private communication, Dr. Jörn Löhken).

2. Material and methods

2.1 Laboratory setup

2.1.1 Technical setup

Oscillatory pore-pressure tests were performed in the perforation laboratory of DynaEnergetics, Troisdorf, where rock samples can be perforated under *in-situ* conditions. The present construction is composed of three pressure systems: confining or overburden, wellbore- and pore pressure (Fig. 2.1). During the perforation, the charge is mounted in the volume in front of the cylinder face and pressurized by the wellbore pressure system. In the following sections, the wellbore system is referred to upstream and the pore pressure system to downstream reservoir because they correspond to the system parts where the pore pressure oscillation is excited and monitored, respectively. With this construction, perforation and also various flow tests are possible.

Figure 2.1: A fluid saturated cylindrical sample is installed in the pressure vessel. The wellbore pressure and pore pressure are applied at the opposing faces whilst the confining pressure is generated on the shell surface.

For the experimental setup of the periodic interference and injectivity tests, an upstream reservoir for the pressure or flow excitation and a downstream reservoir for pressure measurements are required. To ensure the fluid flow into the perforation canal, a cover plate with a single inlet and a mounted seal are used while the shell surface is completely sealed.

A fast external pump is connected to the wellbore pressure system to perform high frequency oscillations about 1 Hz and higher. The oscillation is produced with a function generator connected to the control unit of the excitation pump. While wellbore pressure and pore pressure were recorded and stored by the built-in controller of the perforation system, the volume entering or leaving the sample is measured by the pump and recorded on a connected computer using LabVIEW, National Instruments. The excitation pump also provides direct data of the generated pressure that corresponds to the wellbore pressure.

Two different downstream configurations were tested (Fig. 2.2). In configuration a) the pore pressure volume was used as a downstream reservoir while the confining pressure reservoir was sealed. For the alternative downstream configuration the confining pressure reservoir is connected to the rock while the pore pressure reservoir is sealed. Thus, the applicability of pumping configuration can be reviewed as the dominating direction of flow may change.

Figure 2.2: a) Pumping configuration with reservoirs located on both ends represented by the wellbore pressure and the pore pressure. b) Pumping configuration with reservoirs located on both ends represented by the wellbore pressure and the confining pressure.

2.1.2 Samples and fluid

Rock samples

The rock samples (Fig. 2.3b) used for the perforation test and the oscillatory measurements have cylindrical shape. The sample length is about 60 cm and has a radius of 8.9 cm whereas the shot length varies with rock and perforation characteristics (Fig. 2.3a). Typical reservoir rocks from different lithologies were selected for the tests. Overall, three cylindrical samples from two different lithologies were tested that differ in hydraulic properties and type of perforation (Table 2.1). A Berea sandstone, sample 1, and a Roter Main sandstone, sample 2, were tested with an axial configuration of downstream reservoir (Fig. 2.2a). Another Berea sandstone, sample

3, is referred as reference sample as it was tested using the alternative radial downstream configuration (Fig. 2.2b).

The Berea sandstone and the reference sample were analyzed using the perforation method applied at DynaEnergetics. The Roter Main sandstone was prepared with a drilled canal in comparison to the perforated samples. The drilling by itself does not produce a crushed zone in contrast to explosive perforation processes and allows the comparison of results. During the preparation, the rock samples were physically characterized and saturated with dearomatized hydrocarbon.

Figure 2.3: a) Rock samples before perforation (Photo: Dr. Jörn Löhken). b) Cross section of perforated rock sample with open perforation shot (Photo: Bernd Fricke).

Table 2.1: Rock properties (from private communication, Bernd Fricke and Davood Yosef Nejad)

Parameter	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
Rock type	Berea sandstone	Roter Main sandstone	Berea sandstone
Shot type	perforated	drilled	perforated
Bulk density (kg/m ³)	2174	2252	2180
Porosity (%)	17.64	13.20	17.76
Permeability (mD)	118.39	17.68	-
v_p (m/s)	3117	3316	3130
v_s (m/s)	1590	1644	1646

Fluid

To mimick in-situ conditions, a deaerated hydrocarbon is used in the laboratory perforation test. Different properties of the fluid are required for the evaluation of the performed tests (Table 2.2). A characterization was needed since not all relevant values are provided by the supplier. The fluid density was determined using a pycnometer. Measuring the weight of the empty and the fluid-filled container and the knowledge of the measured volume allows to calculate the density.

$$\rho_f = \frac{m_{\text{pyc+f}} - m_{\text{pyc}}}{V_{\text{pyc}}} \quad (2.1)$$

The calculation of the incompressibility is possible by determining sonic velocities in the fluid. Therefore, the hydrocarbon was filled into a vacuum vessel (Fig. 2.4) enabling contact of the sensors with the fluid. Measuring t_{tot} , the time a signal requires travelling between both sensors without a medium in between, and t_p , the arrival of the P-wave, the velocity calculates after

$$v_w = \frac{t_p - t_{\text{tot}}}{l} \quad (2.2)$$

where l denotes the distance of sensors. The incompressibility is given by the inverse of bulk modulus $1/\kappa = v_p^2 \rho_f$.

Figure 2.4: Vacuum vessel filled with deaerated hydrocarbon and attached ultra sonic sensors connected to a function generator and recording unit.

Table 2.2: Fluid properties provided by Overlack GmbH, Germany, complemented by laboratory measurements

Parameter		
Density	797	[kg/m ³]
Kinematic viscosity	$3.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	[m ² /s]
Dynamic viscosity	0.0255	[Pa · s]
Bulk modulus	$1.36 \cdot 10^9$	[Pa]
Incompressibility	$7.33 \cdot 10^{-10}$	[Pa ⁻¹]

2.1.3 Experimental protocol

The oscillatory pore-pressure tests were performed by sinusoidally oscillating of the fluid pressure in the upstream reservoir and recording the piston volume of the excitation pump, and the pressure in the downstream reservoir. Oscillation frequencies between 0.05 Hz and 2 Hz were used to pump with the aim to explore the speed ability of the excitation pump (Table 2.3). Duration of oscillation was about 60 s, limited by the data record function of the pressure system.

Table 2.3: Performed oscillatory pore-pressure tests

Frequency [Hz]	Color code	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
0.05	●		○	○
0.1	●	○	○	○
0.2	●	○	○	○
0.3	●	○	○	○
0.5	●	○	○	○
1.0	●	○	○	○
1.5	●	○		○
2.0	●			○

2.2 Data analysis

The recorded and saved data requires multiple steps of processing before the calculation of hydraulic properties is possible such as resampling, flow correction and determination of phase shift and amplitude ratio using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). A detrending was not performed since the measured data sets do not contain significant trends. As two different systems record the pressure inside the wellbore pressure system, the data sets were compared to verify consistency on equality on a random basis.

Determination of signal characteristics in frequency domain

The FFT is a mathematical tool, which is able to disassemble a signal into its frequency parts. Transforming the signal from time (Fig. 2.5a) to frequency domain (Fig. 2.5b), the signal now offers the possibility of different and more efficient computational operations. As the transformed data series is split into the occurring frequencies, the investigated signal is easy to be separated from noise.

Figure 2.5: a) Pressure data of the downstream reservoir for a 0.1 Hz oscillation in time domain on Roter Main sandstone. b) Fourier transformed signal of 0.1 Hz oscillation. c) Section of transformed signal displaying the applied frequency.

Figure 2.6: Graphical illustration of phase shift and amplitude ratio. A_1 , A_2 and t_1 , t_2 denote the amplitudes and their corresponding time of both signals whereas T denotes the period length.

When utilizing the FFT for data evaluation of oscillation tests, two other advantages come into effect. Transforming two signals into the frequency domain allows to calculate the phase shift and amplitude ratio separately and correcting the flow data becomes more reliable as later explained in this section. Oscillatory pore-pressure tests rely on the comparison of two signals characterized by their phase and amplitude. The calculation of phase shift and amplitude ratio becomes easier to understand when considered in the time domain (Fig. 2.6):

$$\phi = \frac{t_2 - t_1}{T} \quad (2.3a)$$

$$\delta = \frac{A_2}{A_1} \quad (2.3b)$$

Flow correction

The precise knowledge of flow into the sample is essential for the application of the pore-flow method since the measurement is located at the excitation pump, not in front of the sample. Therefore, the storage capacity S_{sys} of the upstream reservoir needs to be determined. With the calculative approach, the size of upstream V_{res} and fluid incompressibility κ is taken into account:

$$S_{\text{sys}} = \kappa V_{\text{res}} \quad (2.4)$$

The calculated values only represent a part of the reality as the expansibility of the construction or unknown factors are not considered. Thus, further measurements are required to investigate

possible factors affecting the storage capacity. For the realization of an experimental determination of the upstream storage capacity, changes in the laboratory setup are required. The plate ensuring the flow into the perforation shot is changed to a completely closed plate and pressure oscillations are performed. Since the mounted plate was closed the complete access into the perforation shot, no effects relating the sample vessel are covered. Hence, the pressure evolution is plotted against the piston volume of the excitation pump. The storage capacity then corresponds to the first slope and is averaged over all periods.

Table 2.4: Storage capacity

	calculation	measurement
storage capacity (m ³ /Pa)	3·10 ⁻¹²	3.5·10 ⁻¹²

The two determined values coincide sufficiently so a calculative evaluation of the downstream storage capacity is reasonable. The determination for the downstream reservoir is necessary since the pore-pressure analysis for 1D harmonic flow is based on the knowledge of both up- and downstream reservoir storage capacity but direct measurements in the downstream reservoir were technically not possible. The corrected flow Q_{eff} can now be calculated like:

$$Q_{\text{eff}} = Q_{\text{meas}} - S_{\text{sys}}\dot{p} \quad (2.5)$$

where Q_{meas} is the calculated flow rate from observed piston volume. This kind of calculation also involves the derivative of the pressure \dot{p} which must be realized by using a differential quotient. Calculating a derivative from data may cause problems as it includes a phase shift. To avoid this cause of errors, the flow correction can be performed in the frequency domain:

$$F(Q_{\text{eff}}) = F(Q_{\text{meas}}) - i\omega S_{\text{sys}}F(p) \quad (2.6)$$

2.3 Determination of hydraulic properties

The exploitation of gained data requires the calculation of suitable models derived by solving the diffusion equation

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = D\vec{\nabla}p \quad (2.7)$$

where p and D denote fluid pressure and hydraulic diffusivity. A matching coordinate system for present geometry must be found. Various models for specific applications can be calculated by setting up different geometries and boundary conditions (eg. Renner and Messar, 2006; Song and Renner, 2007; Kranz et al., 1990; Fischer, 1992). Thus, solutions for or corresponding to phase shift and amplitude ratio are defined compared to the measured values and translated

back to the quested hydraulic properties. The hydraulic diffusivity D (m^2s^{-1}) used in equation (2.7) is defined by the ratio of transmissivity T (m^2s^{-1}), a transport property, and storativity S (-), a storage property.

$$D = \frac{T}{S} \quad (2.8)$$

Three different diffusion models are used and presented in this report. The first model is the 1D harmonic flow for the pore-pressure analysis which determines permeability k and specific storage capacity s over a grid search for complex parameters and then calculates the diffusivity D with k and s . The second model used assumes radial flow in two concentric layers with a no-flow boundary. In this solution, the diffusivity is calculated from a complex parameter determined with the phase shift. Transmissivity and storativity are generated with use of a Bessel modulus estimated with the complex parameter. A third model for radial diffusion in one concentric layer with no-flow boundary is used as a verification for the second model as it constitutes a special case of two equal layers. A solution for a radial diffusion model with two layers and a constant pressure boundary to analyze the data compiled by the alternative downstream configuration presented in section 2.1.1 was not calculated as these data series only constitute a verification of concept.

The hydraulic properties of the crushed zone are of interest. Hence, an estimation of depth reached with the pressure and flow oscillation is necessary. Generally, the pore-pressure analysis generates information involving the whole sample length due to the essential record of downstream pressure. Whereas, pore-flow analysis can reveal properties of smaller volume such as the crushed zone.

2.3.1 Pore-pressure method

The evaluation of up- and downstream pressure is performed with the aim of getting information about the entire sample, not differentiating the crushed zone in contrast to unimpaired rock. Accordingly, a model for 1D harmonic flow through a homogeneous isotropic sample located between an up- and downstream reservoir was applied (Kranz et al., 1990; Fischer, 1992). For a 1D flow, the diffusion equation simplifies as:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} \quad (2.9)$$

In further work of Song and Renner (2007), x denotes the distance to the downstream reservoir. In combination with a harmonic excitation of upstream pressure

$$p_u = P_u \exp(i\omega t) \quad (2.10)$$

and a consideration of dimensionless storage and transport parameters, the pressure dependent of time and place can be calculated (Bernabé et al., 2004; Bernabé et al., 2006).

$$\xi = \frac{AL}{S_d} \beta_s \quad (2.11)$$

$$\eta_{pp} = \frac{AT}{\pi \mu L S_d} k \quad (2.12)$$

where A , L , S_d , β_s , ν and k denote the cross section of the sample, the length of the sample, the downstream reservoir storage capacity, the specific storage capacity, the dynamic viscosity, and the permeability, respectively. With this pressure formulated analytically for up- and downstream reservoir, the amplitude ratio and phase shift are simply formed by ratio and phase of ratio (Song and Renner, 2007):

$$\delta_{pp} = \frac{p_{\text{down}}}{p_{\text{up}}} = \frac{1}{\left| \cosh \left[(1+i) \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{\eta_{pp}}} \right] + \frac{1+i}{\sqrt{\xi \eta_{pp}}} \sinh \left[(1+i) \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{\eta_{pp}}} \right] \right|} \quad (2.13)$$

$$\phi_{pp} = \arg \left(\frac{p_{\text{down}}}{p_{\text{up}}} \right) = \arg \left(\frac{1}{\left| \cosh \left[(1+i) \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{\eta_{pp}}} \right] + \frac{1+i}{\sqrt{\xi \eta_{pp}}} \sinh \left[(1+i) \sqrt{\frac{\xi}{\eta_{pp}}} \right] \right|} \right) \quad (2.14)$$

By performing a grid search, the dimensionless parameters ξ and η_{pp} are determined and inverted over permeability and specific storage capacity into a diffusivity (Song and Renner, 2007).

$$D = \frac{k}{\mu \beta_s} = \frac{\pi L^2 \eta_{pp}}{T_0 \xi} \quad (2.15)$$

where T_0 is the oscillation period. The storativity is calculated via the specific storage capacity (Renner and Messar, 2006)

$$S = \beta_s \rho_f g L \quad (2.16)$$

and then used in combination with the diffusivity to generate a transmissivity after equation (2.7):

$$T = SD \quad (2.17)$$

2.3.2 Pore-flow method

Solution for radial flow through two concentric layers with a flow boundary

The most suitable radial flow model for the used configuration is constructed by two layers with a no-flow boundary on the outside (Fig. 2.7). This opens the possibility of an isolated consideration of hydraulic parameters of the crushed zone depending on achieved penetration depth. Analogous to the pore-pressure method, the diffusion equation must be solved for the present geometry and boundary conditions. A cylindrical coordinate system is suitable for the radial symmetry of the sample, modifying the diffusion equation to

$$\frac{1}{D} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \quad (2.18)$$

Via separation of variables under consideration of $T_0 = 2\pi/\omega$ and boundary condition $p_i(t) = p_0 \exp(i\omega t)$, the equation transforms to:

$$\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} - \frac{i\omega}{D} P = 0 \quad (2.19)$$

Representing the Bessel differential equation which is solved by the general solution

$$P(r) = A_1 K_0(\eta r) + B_1 I_0(\eta r) \quad (2.20)$$

I_0 and K_0 denote the modified Bessel function of first and second kind and zero order. The constants A and B will be determined in the following.

Figure 2.7: Geometry used for the solution of the diffusion equation for a radial model with two concentric layers and no-flow boundary. r_i and r_d denote the outside boundaries of the layer whereas the interior boundary is described by $r_b = r_c$. Permeabilities k_1 , k_2 and diffusivities D_1 , D_2 are set for the respective layer.

The complex parameter η in the argument of I_0 and K_0 functions as a calculation variable for the hydraulic rock properties involving the diffusivity (Renner and Messar, 2006):

$$\eta = \sqrt{\frac{i\omega}{D}} \quad (2.21)$$

With the use of Darcy's law

$$q(x) = -\frac{k}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \quad (2.22)$$

and the derivatives of the modified Bessel function

$$\frac{\partial I_{0(\eta r)}}{\partial r} = \eta \frac{\partial I_{1(\eta r)}}{\partial r} \quad (2.23)$$

$$\frac{\partial K_{0(\eta r)}}{\partial r} = -\eta \frac{\partial K_{1(\eta r)}}{\partial r} \quad (2.24)$$

the flux q is calculated:

$$q(r) = \frac{k\eta}{\mu} A_1 K_{1(\eta r)} - \frac{k\eta}{\mu} B_1 I_{1(\eta r)} \quad (2.25)$$

As we need a flow rate Q_i for the phase shift and amplitude ratio, the relation $k/\mu = T/(\rho gh)$ at $r = r_i$ (Fig. 2.7) is used:

$$Q_{i(t)} = -2\pi r_i \frac{T}{\rho g} q_{i(t)} \quad (2.26)$$

To solve the equation, the formulation of the describing boundary conditions is needed. Therefore, Darcy's law, pressure, and flow continuity at the interface $r_b = r_c$ (Fig. 2.7) and a no-flow boundary at r_d are used

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} = -\frac{q\mu}{k} \quad (2.27)$$

$$p_b = p_c \quad (2.28)$$

$$q_b = q_c \quad (2.29)$$

$$q_d = 0 \quad (2.30)$$

In combination with the general solution of the Bessel differential equation, the boundary condition read as:

$$-A_1 K_{1(\eta_1 r_i)} + B_1 I_{1(\eta_1 r_i)} = -\frac{q\mu}{k_1 \eta_1} \quad (2.31)$$

$$A_1 K_{0(\eta_1 r_b)} + B_1 I_{0(\eta_1 r_b)} = A_2 K_{0(\eta_2 r_c)} + B_2 I_{0(\eta_2 r_c)} \quad (2.32)$$

$$\frac{k_1 \eta_1}{\mu} A_1 K_{1(\eta_1 r_b)} - \frac{k_1 \eta_1}{\mu} B_1 I_{1(\eta_1 r_b)} = \frac{k_2 \eta_2}{\mu} A_2 K_{1(\eta_2 r_c)} - \frac{k_2 \eta_2}{\mu} B_2 I_{1(\eta_2 r_c)} \quad (2.33)$$

$$\frac{k_2 \eta_2}{\mu} A_2 K_{1(\eta_2 r_d)} - \frac{k_2 \eta_2}{\mu} B_2 I_{1(\eta_2 r_d)} = 0 \quad (2.34)$$

The four equations (2.31) to (2.34) contain four unknown factors A_1 , B_1 , A_2 , B_2 , creating a system of equation to be solved (see Appendix A). As for the comparison of phase shift and amplitude ratio at $r = r_i$ only A_1 and B_1 are needed, the two left constants were not determined. Phase shift ϕ and Bessel modulus B modulus which corresponds to the amplitude ratio are calculated according to section 2.3.1.

$$B = \left| \frac{Q_{i(t)}}{p_{i(t)}} \right| = \frac{-2\pi r_i \frac{T}{\rho g h} \left(\frac{k_1 \eta_1}{\mu} A_1 K_{1(\eta_1 r_i)} - \frac{k_1 \eta_1}{\mu} B_1 I_{1(\eta_1 r_i)} \right)}{A_1 K_{0(\eta_1 r_i)} + B_1 I_{0(\eta_1 r_i)}} \quad (2.35)$$

$$\phi_{\text{qp}} = \arg \left(\frac{Q_{i(t)}}{p_{i(t)}} \right) = \arg \left(\frac{-2\pi r_i \frac{T}{\rho g h} \left(\frac{k_1 \eta_1}{\mu} A_1 K_{1(\eta_1 r_i)} - \frac{k_1 \eta_1}{\mu} B_1 I_{1(\eta_1 r_i)} \right)}{A_1 K_{0(\eta_1 r_i)} + B_1 I_{0(\eta_1 r_i)}} \right) \quad (2.36)$$

Calculation of hydraulic parameters

The hydraulic parameters can now be determined by a comparison of observed phase shift and amplitude ratio and analytical model. By comparing the measured phase shift to the model, a value for η is derived (Fig. 2.8a) and is used with the applied frequency to calculate the diffusivity.

$$D = \frac{\omega r_i^2}{\eta^2} \quad (2.37)$$

To find the transmissivity T , η is used to find a value for the Bessel modulus B (Fig. 2.8b). The connection to transmissivity is drawn over the relation of measured amplitude ratio and Bessel modulus:

$$\delta_{\text{qp}} = \frac{2\pi r_i T}{\rho g} B \quad (2.38)$$

With knowledge of transmissivity and diffusivity, the storativity simply follows equation (2.17). The penetration depth r_p reached of the pore flow method is estimated from a simple scaling relation (Turcotte and Schubert, 1982).

$$r_p \sim \sqrt{DT_0} \quad (2.39)$$

Figure 2.8: a) Determination of complex parameter η by comparing the observed phase shift ϕ to the solution for theoretical phase calculated for η . b) Using the in a) determined value of η to find the corresponding Bessel modulus B .

Radial flow in one concentric layer with a flow boundary

Since the solution for a radial model with a no-flow boundary (Fig. 2.9) was introduced by Renner and Messar (2006), it provides the possibility of verifying the radial flow model for two layers with a no-flow boundary calculated here. By entering equal hydraulic properties, the two layer model should converge to the one layer model. This prove is also necessary for the data analysis because of the tests that were performed on drilled unperforated samples.

Figure 2.9: Geometry used for the solution of the diffusion equation for a radial model with one concentric layer and no-flow boundary. R and r_i denote the boundaries of the layer which is assigned with permeability k and diffusivity D .

For the one layer case, the solutions for phase shift and amplitude ratio are:

$$\delta_{\text{fbpp}} = \left| \frac{K_{1(\eta R)} I_{0(\eta r)} + K_0 \eta r I_{1(\eta R)}}{K_{1(\eta R)} I_{0(\eta r_i)} + K_0 \eta r_i I_{1(\eta R)}} \right| \quad (2.40)$$

$$\phi_{\text{fbpp}} = \arg \left(\frac{K_{1(\eta R)} I_{0(\eta r)} + K_0 \eta r I_{1(\eta R)}}{K_{1(\eta R)} I_{0(\eta r_i)} + K_0 \eta r_i I_{1(\eta R)}} \right) \quad (2.41)$$

Graphical illustration of diffusion model solution space

The solution for the radial diffusion equation with two concentric layers and a no-flow boundary was evaluated for different ratios in η and thicknesses of the crushed zone. The calculation of the explicit solution is realized by the complex parameter η as argument of the used Bessel functions introduced in section 2.3.2. Since the connection between Bessel modulus and amplitude ratio involves the transmissivity (see equation (2.38)), a explicit vertical position of potential model remains an uncertainty without further information.

The sets of solutions for a variation in permeability (Fig. 2.10) and thickness (Fig. 2.11) of the crushed zone show the same behaviour towards the calculation boundaries. For a maximizing diffusivity the models approximate 25 % phase shift. A vanishing diffusivity leads a phase shift of 12.5 % which corresponds to the estimated value for a 1D flow (Renner and Messar, 2006). The solution for a lowering in η ratio moves towards lower phase shifts and shows a small bend at the phase shift minimum of the solution for the one layer case. The graphs for the lowest ratios 0.01 and 0.1 do not reach the boundary at 12.5 % which is explained by the limited calculation length. Increasing ratios for η cause a flattening of the phase shift minima leading to solutions proceeding directly between the boundaries.

A variation in thickness of the crushed zone only shows an influence on the upper part of the solution. An additional curvature or rather a second minima of phase shift is created on the upper branch of solutions. For decreasing thicknesses, the curve propagates to higher shifts, even higher than 12.5 % before returning towards the unaltered boundaries.

Figure 2.10: Analytic solution of the radial diffusion equation for two concentric layers with a no-flow boundary and variations in hydraulic properties of crushed zone. The special case of $\eta_1/\eta_2 = 1$ whereas η_1 denotes the complex parameter representing the crushed zone and η_2 the destroyed rock corresponds to the radial diffusion model for one concentric layer with a no-flow boundary.

Figure 2.11: Analytic solution of the radial diffusion equation for two concentric layers with a no-flow boundary and variations in thickness of crushed zone. Variations ranging from 4 to 12 mm are displayed.

2.4 Numerical modelling

The implementation of oscillatory pore-pressure tests with new boundary conditions benefits from complementing simulations. A study on the variation of effective parameters exhibits information on the sensitivity of simulation and allows a comparison with the predictions of the analytical model. Using COMSOL Multiphysics, numerical modelling for simplified geometries was performed and analyzed analogous to the laboratory experiments. The software is built for numerical simulations of physical processes that can be characterized by differential equations. The finite element method is used to solve the given equation numerically.

COMSOL's user interface works with a structured work flow. In the beginning, the dimension of the model geometry must be defined, in this case a 2D axes-symmetric environment (Fig. 2.12a). Simulations in a 2D environment reduce calculation time and generates a 3D model by transferring the data using the symmetry (Fig. 2.12b). In the next step, parameters and variables that are needed to set up the model and its environment were entered. The geometry is built by using the set parameters creating different geometrical object which assemble the final model. To create a suitable cylinder with two concentric layers and a perforation shot, the calculation of differences between object volumes is required. The volume of a cylinder representing the volume of crushed zone and perforation shot is removed from the sample cylinder.

Figure 2.12: a) 2D axis symmetric model of a cylindrical rock volume with a separated volume representing the crushed zone. The source term is applied on the blue marked lines whereas all other outlines are set as no-flow boundaries except for the contact to symmetry axis. b) 3D illustration of a simulated model for time step 0.5 s.

A new cylinder is built by subtracting the volume of perforation shot again from the volume of shot and crushed zone . Up- and downstream reservoirs were not created since the dominating influence of upstream reservoir is represented by its storage capacity. Therefore, only the influence of fluid incompressibility would be taken into account, neglecting unknown factors caused by the laboratory setup. Hydraulic properties of the two concentric layers can be defined during the process of geometry building. The appropriate differential equation with boundary and initial conditions is implemented. A mesh for the calculation process is created whereby the difference in size of objects must be considered. A mesh suitable for bigger objects may not provide enough calculation points for smaller parts. In the last step before simulating, the type of study is defined. In this case a time dependent study is needed. The simulated data is exported and evaluated analogous to the laboratory data. The PDE provided by COMSOL

$$e_a \frac{\partial^2 \vec{p}}{\partial t^2} + d_a \frac{\partial \vec{p}}{\partial t} + \nabla(-c \nabla \vec{p} - \alpha \vec{p} + \gamma) + \beta \nabla \vec{p} + a \vec{p} = \vec{f} \quad (2.42)$$

is compared to the used diffusion equation in a radial coordinate system to define the required coefficients. As permeability is of interest, the coefficients are defined with permeability k and specific storage capacity β_s . Thus, the parameters in the equation correspond with following physical properties.

$$c = k \quad (2.43)$$

$$d_a = \mu_f \beta_s \quad (2.44)$$

$$\vec{f} = k \frac{p_r}{r} \quad (2.45)$$

while all other coefficients equal zero.

$$e_a = 0 \quad (2.46)$$

$$\alpha = 0 \quad (2.47)$$

$$\gamma = 0 \quad (2.48)$$

$$\beta = 0 \quad (2.49)$$

$$a = 0 \quad (2.50)$$

Inserting the parameters into the equation leads to

$$\mu_s \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (-k \nabla p) = k \frac{p_r}{r} \quad (2.51)$$

The source is defined by a pressure oscillation of a set pressure amplitude p_A

$$p = p_A \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T_0} t\right) \quad (2.52)$$

It is applied as a Dirichlet boundary on the faces of the rectangle (Fig. 2.12a) representing the interface of crushed zone and perforation canal. A no-flow boundary is set on the left-over faces of the model which is expressed by:

$$-n \cdot (-c\nabla p - \alpha p + \gamma) = 0 \quad (2.53)$$

The data required for a pore-flow analysis is generated using a 2D cut point on the interface where the pressure source is applied. Pressure data are taken from the solution of the differential equation respectively on this position from the source term. The flow data require further calculations via the law of Darcy. The flow is calculated integrating over the pressure along the two excitation interfaces:

$$q = -\frac{k_c}{\mu_f} 2\pi r_p \left(\int p_r dr + \int p_z dz \right) \quad (2.54)$$

Here, k_c , μ_f , p_r , p_z and r_p denote the permeability of the crushed zone, the dynamic viscosity of the fluid, the pressure along the r axis, the pressure along the z axis, and the radius of the perforation shot, respectively. In addition to the complementing laboratory results and analytical model, the simulation is used to investigate the influence of change in effective parameters. Thus, the permeability and the thickness of the crushed zone were varied over the simulation (Table 2.5). Different frequencies were used to examine trends and theoretical possible penetration depths.

Table 2.5: Parameters for numerical simulation

Test	Thickness of crushed zone (mm)	Permeability of crushed zone (m ²)	specific storage capacity (Pa ⁻¹)
1	1...15	10 ⁻¹⁴	10 ⁻¹⁰
2	5	10 ⁻¹⁴ ...10 ⁻¹⁶	10 ⁻¹⁰

3. Results

3.1 Pore-pressure analysis

Berea sandstone

Phase shifts for the Berea sandstone sample range from 21.4 % to 53.7 % for frequencies from 0.1 to 0.5 Hz, respectively. Analogues, the negative logarithm to the basis of 10 of the amplitude ratio increases for 0.1 Hz to 0.5 Hz from 0.5 to 1.2 but then decreases for the highest frequencies of 1 Hz and 1.5 Hz from 0.3 to 0.6. Only the data for 0.1 to 0.5 Hz fall within the grid of ξ and η representing the solution space for 1D diffusion. The error determined for the phase shift of 0.1 to 0.5 Hz ranges from 2 % increasing to 5 % in a dimension which allows to determine a values via grid search. The obtained error for oscillation frequencies which fit the solution space increase with increasing frequency. The error bars enable an allocation to different grid lines but except for the data of 0.1 Hz the data plots in areas of wide spread grid. Frequencies of 1 and 1.5 Hz exhibit large uncertainties for the phase shift of 27.6 and 29.8 % whereas the errors of amplitude ratio follow the trend of lower frequencies.

Figure 3.1: Berea sandstone: The calculated phase shift and amplitude ratio of the up- and downstream pressure are plotted in the grid plot of ξ and η_{pp} under consideration of their error bars.

Roter Main sandstone

The determined phase shifts of the test on the Roter Main sandstone range between 23 % and 56 %, correlating the frequency. The highest value appears for a frequency of 1 Hz which was the highest tested oscillation frequency in this data series. The smallest amplitude ratio was found for 0.1 Hz of 0.9. The ratio increases with frequency to 1.5 for 0.5 Hz. The only exceptions are the results for 1.0 Hz of 1.1. Comparing the data to the solution space again, only the lower frequencies are covered. The error for the phase shift of the included data is small compared to the frequencies located out of the borders of the model. The uncertainties for 0.5 and 1 Hz of 10.3 and 29.9 % allow possible values of phase shift covered by the solution space. Though, the error bars cross areas of very narrow grid lines and therefore the data points do not constitute useful information.

Figure 3.2: Roter Main sandstone: The calculated phase shift and amplitude ratio of the up- and downstream pressure are plotted in the grid plot of ξ and η_{pp} under consideration of their error bars.

Hydraulic Parameters

The hydraulic properties of Berea and Roter Main sandstone were determined for the data fitting the diffusion model. The results for diffusivities (Fig. 3.3) show the same trend for both samples. With higher frequencies the value decreases. The diffusivities calculated for the Berea sandstone range from 0.295 to 0.071 m²/s. Slightly lower values of 0.185 to 0.054 m²/s were determined for the Roter Main sandstone.

Permeabilities of the Roter Main sandstone determined with the pore-pressure analysis (Fig. 3.4) range from $4.3 \cdot 10^{-12}$ to $1.8 \cdot 10^{-12}$ m². The values deviate two orders from the source rock

permeability of $1.7 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$. For the Berea sandstone, similar permeabilities of $1.2 \cdot 10^{-11}$ to $2.0 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$ were determined. The permeability of the source rock correlates $1.2 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2$.

Figure 3.3: Diffusivities plotted against frequencies determined from pore-pressure analysis. All data for Berea sandstone and Roter Main sandstone locating inside the solution space for ξ and η were evaluated.

Figure 3.4: Permeabilities determined from pore-pressure analysis of Berea and Roter Main sandstone. Dashed lines represent the respective permeabilities of the source rock from laboratory experiments performed by DynaEnergetics (Table 2.1).

3.2 Pore-flow analysis

Phase shift and amplitude ratio were calculated from the data sets of Berea and Roter Main sandstone and were plotted with solutions for a variation of η ratios since the measured data locate in an area where the different solutions for varying thicknesses of the crushed zone are very narrow and no clear allocation would be possible.

Berea sandstone

The range of phase shifts measured on the Berea sandstone starts at 12.48 % for the oscillation test with 1.5 Hz and ends at 24.58 % for 0.5 Hz. The data for 0.1 Hz to 1.5 Hz show a decrease of shift with increasing frequency whereas the value for 0.5 Hz seems to match no trend. The amplitude ratios also exhibit no significant change with frequency. All data points were plotted with their respective error but neither phase shift nor amplitude ratio deviations show influential sizes concerning model applicability. When compared to the possible suitable models, the data arrange between solutions for an increased η . No clear similarity is noticeable but still an evaluation would be possible.

Figure 3.5: Estimated phase shifts and amplitude ratios of the Berea sandstone are plotted in the solution space of the presented diffusion model. Different frequencies are marked by the color code introduced in table 2.3. Error bars for phase shift and amplitude ratio exceed symbol sizes.

Roter Main sandstone

The phase shifts determined for the five tested frequencies arrange in a similar dimension in comparison to the data of the Berea sandstone. The lowest shift of 18 % was calculated from

the test with the highest used frequency of 1.5 Hz. For 0.3 Hz, the highest phase shift is 24.23 %. Indeed, the formation of data seems random though an increasing trend for values of 0.1 to 0.3 Hz is visible. Measurements of amplitude ratio sketch a more consistent result. A decrease of ratio from 1 Hz to 0.1 Hz is observable, only the result for 1.5 Hz seems to be an outlier. Calculated errors display a conspicuousness as the range of error for 0.5 Hz is 12 % whereby the other data exhibit ranges under 1 %. Like the results of the pore-flow analysis on the Berea sandstone, the measured data concentrates in the area of increased eta factors and mismatch the analytic solutions.

Figure 3.6: Estimated phase shifts and amplitude ratios of the Roter Main sandstone are plotted in the solution space of the presented diffusion models. Different frequencies are marked by the color code introduced in table 2.3. Error bars were plotted for all results but hardly exceed symbol size in most cases.

Reference sample

Oscillatory pore-pressure tests were performed for pore-flow analysis with an alternative downstream configuration (Fig. 2.2b). The determined phase shifts and amplitude ratios exhibit differences comparing the results from the initial downstream geometry (Fig. 2.2a). The phase shift and amplitude ratio of 0.05 to 0.3 Hz decrease slightly. The higher frequencies show a decrease in phase shift from 15.9 % to 10.5 %. The data of 0.5 Hz was not plotted since the determined phase shift of -6 % is negative and has a uncertainty of 46 %. The determined errors of correctly analysed data increase with frequency. The only exception is represented by 0.1 Hz. The calculated error is 29.5 % and therefore only plotted in positive direction as negative bar exceeding zero in a logarithmic plot is not realizable.

Figure 3.7: Phase shift and amplitude ratio of upstream flow and pressure determined from the reference sample. Different frequencies are marked by the color code introduced in table 2.3. Measurements on this sample were performed using an alternative downstream configuration (Fig. 2.2b). The results were plotted with the analytic solution of the radial diffusion equation in two concentric layers with a no-flow boundary. The model does not describe the present flow regime but illustrates the results in comparison to the previous described phase shifts and amplitude ratios.

3.3 Numerical modelling

The data gained from the numerical simulation using COMSOL results from variations of two effective parameters in separate data series while all other properties were kept constant. Variations of permeability and thickness of the crushed zone were simulated with a set of typical frequencies performed in the laboratory experiments (Table 2.5). The results were compared to analytical models derived with the input values of the respective simulation. A calculation of hydraulic properties was performed for data sets which sufficiently fit the models.

The errors of phase shift and amplitude ratio were calculated and plotted. Since the uncertainties depend on the sinusoidality and trend of signals, errors for the numerical simulation are very small. Phase shift errors range from orders of 10^{-2} to 10^{-6} % and amplitude errors from orders of 10^{-16} to 10^{-20} m³/s/Pa. All explicit data can be found in table 5.8 and 5.9 in Appendix B.

3.3.1 Variation in permeability of crushed zone

The permeability was modified over three orders of magnitude from 10^{-14} to 10^{-16} m² while the permeability of the outer layer was set constantly to 10^{-13} m². The results for phase shift and amplitude ratio exhibit different trends matching to the respective analytic solution. Phase shifts calculated from a crushed zone permeability of 10^{-14} m² decrease with frequency and range from 22.9 to 11.3 %. With decreasing frequency, the amplitude ratios increase ranging from $8.9 \cdot 10^{-13}$ to $6.2 \cdot 10^{-12}$ m³/s/Pa. With higher frequency, the distance to the analytical model increases. For a simulated permeability of 10^{-15} m², the data is shifted towards smaller phase shifts and larger amplitude ratios following the prediction of the analytic solution. Phase shifts range from 15.6 to 2.6 % and amplitude ratios from $7.5 \cdot 10^{-13}$ to $1.4 \cdot 10^{-12}$ m³/s/Pa. The deviations from the model are decreasing with higher frequencies. The data of the crushed zone permeability of 10^{-16} m² display a different trend than the previous data sets. The phase shift increases from 0.1 to 0.5 Hz and decreases afterwards for 1 and 1.5 Hz. The amplitude ratio slightly increases consistently from $1.48 \cdot 10^{-13}$ to $1.53 \cdot 10^{-13}$ m³/s/Pa. Although the data follow the analytic solution, a further analysis towards hydraulic properties is not possible since phase shifts and amplitude ratios exceed the calculation limit.

Figure 3.8: Phase shift and amplitude ratio determined from numerical simulation of hydraulic diffusion. Variations of permeability were simulated for four different frequencies distinguishable by the color code introduced in table 2.3. The thick lines represent the respective analytic solution for each data set. The permeability of the destroyed rock set to 10^{-13} m² while the the value for the crushed zone was changed to a) 10^{-14} m², b) 10^{-15} m², c) 10^{-16} m².

Diffusivities (Fig. 3.9) were calculated for the data sets of 10^{-14} m² and 10^{-15} m² permeability of crushed zone. The data set of decreased permeability of one order obtains nearly constant diffusivities close to the input value. Whereas, diffusivities calculated for a decrease of two orders of permeability decrease with increasing oscillation frequency. Both data sets show significantly lower diffusivities than the simulation input for the outer layer, the source rock.

Penetration depths (Fig. 3.10) gained from the diffusivity data exhibit a decrease of depth with increasing frequency. The depth ranges from 0.45 to 0.15 m for the permeability of 10^{-14} m² and from 0.20 to 0.004 m for 10^{-15} m².

Figure 3.9: Diffusivity calculated for the simulated data of the variation in permeability of the crushed zone. The three data sets were evaluated with the respective properties for the radial diffusion model.

Figure 3.10: Penetration depth of permeability variation simulation estimated with use of diffusivity data and corresponding period following equation (2.39).

3.3.2 Variation in thickness of crushed zone

The size of crushed zone was modified in four steps from 1 to 15 mm. The appearing phase shifts of the data series simulated with a thickness of 1 mm decrease with higher frequency and range

from 23.7 to 14.9 %. Whereas, the amplitude ratio increases with range of $9.2 \cdot 10^{-13}$ to $8.0 \cdot 10^{-12}$ $\text{m}^3/\text{s}/\text{Pa}$. With increasing frequencies, the gained data deviate more from the analytical model. The data determined for a thickness of 5 mm display a similar behaviour extended towards smaller phase shifts. The amplitude ratio maintains values of the previous dimensions. The extension of phase shift continues for thicknesses of 10 and 15 mm for the crushed zone. Considering the change in analytical model with increasing crushed zone thickness, an opposing trend relating the simulation data is noticeable. With thicker crushed zone, the curvature towards lower phase shifts gets smaller.

Figure 3.11: Phase shift and amplitude ratio determined from numerically simulated data plotted with the solutions of radial diffusion equation for two concentric layers with a no-flow boundary for corresponding thicknesses. Different frequencies are marked by the color code introduced in table 2.3. The thick lines represent the respective analytic solution for each data set. In all simulations the permeability of the crushed zone was set one order of magnitude higher with regard to the undestroyed rock. Thicknesses of a) 1 mm, b) 5 mm, c) 10 mm, d) 15 mm were tested.

Figure 3.12: Diffusivity calculated for the simulated data of the variation in thickness of the crushed zone. The four data sets were evaluated with the respective properties for the radial diffusion model.

Figure 3.13: Penetration depth estimated from diffusivities gained by simulation of variation of thickness of the crushed zone.

Diffusivities were calculated for all data and display a similar behaviour. The diffusivity increases slightly with increasing frequency. Except for the calculated values for 1 and 1.5 Hz simulated on a thickness of 1 mm of the crushed zone, all data series are found smaller than the input diffusivity of crushed zone. The largest diffusivities are found for a thickness of 1 mm, ranging from 0.031 to 0.052 m²/s. The smallest values appear for a thickness of 15 mm, ranging from 0.014 to 0.022 m²/s.

Penetration depths estimated from the diffusivities of the variations of crushed zone thickness display a non-linear negative trend with increasing frequency. The highest depth appears for the thinnest simulation of crushed zone ranging from 0.56 to 0.19 m. Increasing the size of crushed zone leads to lower penetration depths. The smallest depths are exhibited by largest crushed zone ranging from 0.37 to 0.12 m.

4. Discussion

4.1 Identification of error sources in pore-flow method for perforated rock samples

The investigation of the hydraulic properties of the crushed zone requires an experimental method that probes only a part of the rock sample. Therefore, a pore-flow method was applied with high frequency oscillations which is producing shallow penetration depths. An analytic solution for the radial diffusion equation was derived accounting for the appropriate boundary and initial conditions. The geometry is represented by a model with two concentric layers with a no-flow boundary. To assess the applicability of the model for the flow regime occurring in the experiments, a numerical simulation that reduces the simplifications regarding infinite vertical extension inherent to the analytical model was performed.

The dominating influence on the experimental data was found as an insufficient determination of the upstream storage capacity causing a large deviation from the analytic solution.

Figure 4.1: Phase shift and amplitude ratio obtained from upstream flow and pressure data measured on Berea sandstone corrected with a hypothetical storage capacity of $7 \text{ m}^3/\text{Pa}$. The vertical uncertainty occurs because of the missing knowledge of transmissivity as explained in section 2.3.2. Different frequencies are marked by the color code introduced in table 2.3.

To investigate the influence of the uncertainty in the storage capacity of the upstream reservoir, the data set of Berea sandstone was corrected with a storage capacity of $7 \text{ m}^3/\text{Pa}$, i.e. twice

the measured storage capacity (Table 2.4) was chosen. A change in storage capacity of less than one order shows a massive impact on the correction of flow. Not only the overall location of data points but also the trend is corrected to an appearance fitting the radial diffusion equation solved for two concentric layers with a no-flow boundary. Matching the hypothesis of an insufficient determination of storage capacity, the data used for pore-pressure analysis show no significant deviation from the analytic solution as the storage capacity affects only flow, not pressure. To address this problem, a method must be found to implement the sample vessel into an experimental determination of the upstream characteristics. One possibility might be the use of a calibration sample while performing storage capacity measurements with the sample vessel connected to the upstream reservoir. A cylinder made of an impermeable material is required, for example steel or granite.

The data obtained from the tests deviate significantly from the predictions of the analytical model. The determined phase shifts show magnitudes which are also observable in solutions for radial diffusion models as they do not exceed 25 %. However, the experimental data do not match to the progression of model solutions calculated for a variation in thickness and diffusivity of the crushed zone in reasonable extent. The observed trend for change in frequency resembles a mirrored version of the model curve for radial flow, probably a coincidence. This mismatch indicates a much more complex flow regime than assumed or other unknown factors in laboratory setup influence the measurements. To ensure a radial flow, a change in downstream configuration was applied (Fig. 2.2b). The results of the measurements with the alternative setup were supposed to reveal whether the flow and pressure signals in first place recognize the flow boundary and the change in geometry. However, no significant improvement regarding the match between observations and model was possible as the results differ only slightly from the initial axial setup. The presented radial flow model is not suitable for a description of the alternative configuration. Boundary conditions describing the present case are also presented by radial diffusion with two concentric layers but the outer boundary changed. The definition of boundary condition depends on the occurrence of a pressure signal in the downstream reservoir. If a pressure signal is detectable, the boundary condition is represented by a defined pressure or else by a constant pressure boundary. As the trend of solution for radial diffusion with a constant pressure boundary was already introduced (Renner and Messar, 2006), the assumption of the data mismatching also the model for two layers seems to be an educated guess. Hence, other effects than the downstream configuration are influencing the laboratory measurements or the analytic solution is not able to describe the present experimental setup.

Addressing reasons accountable for the large deviations of obtained data, issues in the experimental setup are considered. Different sources of errors might occur since the laboratory set-up was not designed for oscillatory pore-pressure tests. The setup was built to generate high fluid pressures during perforation tests and therefore combines high pressure pipes with a diameter in millimeter scale and volumes in centimeter scale accommodating the shaped

charges. The oscillatory testing took place in absence of a charge. Thus, components of the upstream reservoir differ largely in size and turbulent flow might occur. Another crucial source of error is as introduced constituted by the determination of storage capacity used for the flow correction. As mentioned in section 2.2, the experimental estimation of storage capacity is restricted to the upstream volume from excitation pump to the cover plate in front of the sample. This neglects the influence of volume and other potential impacts located in the sample vessel. The calculative approach involves the fluid filled volume inside the perforation shot. Though, no significant difference relating the experimental approach occurs. A possible influence may appear in the connection area of cover plate and rock sample where the different materials are sealed to ensure the flow into the perforation shot. If this area absorbs just a small amount of fluid, the connection area would represent an unconsidered hydraulic element with a potential big influence on the recorded fluid volume entering and leaving the sample. Since both methods do not include possibly occurring effects like described inside the sample vessel apart from fluid compressibility, the flow correction exhibits an uncertainty whose dimension remains unknown.

4.2 Applicability of radial flow model for perforated rock samples

The results of the numerical simulation answer the question of applicability of the assumed model. The variation of effective parameters of numerical simulation exhibited no significant deviation from analytical models. Therefore, the shortcomings of the analytic solution of the diffusion equation do not cause the mismatch between experimental observations and model prediction.

Variations of effective parameter, permeability, and thickness of crushed zone were investigated in relation to the unchanged source rock. The calculation of respective models was performed under consideration of input values of the numerical simulation. Consequently, all solutions are mathematical completely defined without the vertical uncertainty occurring in the presentation of the laboratory results because of missing information on transmissivity. The obtained phase shifts and amplitude ratios of both data sets, variation in permeability and thickness follow the analytic solutions despite a certain deviation. Slight differences in the simulation results compared to the models are anticipated since the analytic solution considers simplifying assumptions. A major difference is represented by the geometry. The analytic solution assumes an infinite extended sample whereby the simulated geometry is built with no-flow boundaries on the top and bottom face of the sample and the perforation shot ends inside the sample. Hence, flow through the area representing the end of the shot takes place and contributes the discrepancy. Nevertheless, all trends predicted by the analytical model

can clearly be recognized in the results and the analysis of the data sets is possible. The only exception is the data set obtained from simulating three orders of change in permeability of the crushed zone. Indeed, the data do not deviate the model but exceeds the calculation space of the model as it is partly located on the upper branch of the model.

The diffusivities determined of all evaluable data sets show dimensions matching the respective input values except the data set for a change in permeability of two orders. The lowest applied frequency is perfectly located at the given diffusivity while the higher frequencies show increasing deviations. This might result from rising distance to the respective analytical model. The further conversion into penetration depth shows higher values compared to the sample dimensions. Despite the problems in the evaluation of higher frequencies, the trends of penetration depths show that highest technical possible oscillation frequencies are required for an investigation of the crushed zone characteristics. The numerical modelling highlights the robustness of the analytical model regarding changes in geometric details of sample composition and therefore places the focus on the laboratory experiments.

4.3 Hydraulic characterization of entire rock volumes

The application of the pore-pressure method in an axial configuration nominally reveals properties of the rock volume which contributes the flow path connecting up- and downstream reservoir. In the implemented experiments, crushed zone and intact rock potentially represent the contributions to the effective hydraulic properties in axial direction. Beside the possible comparison of gained data with potential results of pore flow method regarding reduction of flow properties for the crushed zone, more information on model applicability can be obtained. Information gained from applicability of the pore-pressure method narrows the search for errors in the pore-flow method.

Analyzing the data determined from fluid pressure of the reservoirs, the dominating source of error was found as high frequency noise in the pressure records (Fig. 2.5a) covering the signal and critically increasing the error for high frequencies. Phase shifts and amplitude ratios can be obtained from oscillations not showing a clear sinusoidal signal in the downstream reservoir (Song and Renner, 2007). The strong noise, however, inhibits the possibility of a visual inspection of a response in the downstream reservoir. A record of the fluid pressure in both reservoirs with an improved signal-to-noise ratio may show if the penetration depth is the prevailing problem or a signal detection of high frequencies can be realized.

Despite the noise, the application of pore-pressure method to perforated rock samples evaluated with a 1D diffusion model with up- and downstream reservoir presented by Song and Renner (2007) is possible in the experimental setup of DynaEnergetics. The fluid pressure in both reservoirs can be recorded with an acceptable signal-to-noise ratio for frequencies below 0.3 Hz for determination of phase shift and amplitude ratio. The comparison of obtained phase

and amplitude data including their uncertainty to the analytical model allows the determination of hydraulic properties. The results slightly vary from the expected behavior as determined permeabilities describing the entire flow path are higher than permeabilities estimated by DynaEnergetics on the respective source rock. The permeabilities deviate about two orders from the source rock data. Furthermore, no significant difference between Berea and Roter Main sandstone concerning the deviation from the source rock permeability is recognizable. This missing difference is unexpected since the Roter Main sandstone was not perforated and thus exhibits no crushed zone influencing the flow characteristics. The values for diffusivity and permeability show a dependency on frequency. Hence, the frequency dependence indicates heterogeneity or inappropriate model underlying the analysis. The application of longer periods might reveal an approximation of diffusivity and permeability towards a constant value. Because at least three periods are required for the determination of phase shift and amplitude ratio, recording times are required exceeding the present limit of 60 s.

The largest errors determined for the pore-pressure analysis occur as stated for high frequencies. The oscillations with 1 and 1.5 Hz on the Berea sandstone and 0.5 and 1 Hz on the Roter Main sandstone show these uncertainties and plot outside the solution space (Fig. 3.1 and 3.2). The large uncertainties in phase shift and amplitude ratio occur although much higher numbers of periods were available and considered than for lower frequencies. The averaging of more periods theoretically decreases the uncertainty. Though the extent of error bars leads to possible locations described by the solution space, the narrow grid near the model limits amplifies the errors by not allowing a clear allocation.

5. Conclusion

We investigated the applicability of oscillatory pore-pressure tests on perforated rock samples with the aim of determination of hydraulic parameters of the crushed zone. For this purpose, we derived an analytic solution of the radial diffusion equation for two concentric layers with a no-flow boundary. Laboratory experiments were performed at DynaEnergetics GmbH Co.KG, Troisdorf, Germany. Perforated and drilled rock samples were placed between an up- and downstream reservoir, a confining pressure was applied, and a pressure excitation in the upstream reservoir was performed. The fluid pressure of both reservoirs and the piston volume of the pump were recorded. Afterwards, the signal characteristics, phase shift, and amplitude ratio were determined and compared to analytical model for pressure and flow analysis. A numerical simulation was performed to examine the influence of variations of effective parameters. Evaluation towards phase shift and amplitude ratio and comparison to the respective model was conducted.

The experimental data for the pore-pressure method matched the applied 1D Diffusion model introduced by Song and Renner (2007). High frequency noise led to critically increasing uncertainties for the estimation of phase shift of the highest applied frequencies. Hydraulic properties were determined for the data with reasonable uncertainties and exhibited a dependence on frequency. The estimation of phase shift and amplitude ratio for the pore-flow method displayed inconsistent results compared to the analytic solution. The observed data cover a plausible range but mismatched the predicted trend. The numeric simulation provided data sets demonstrating the effect of changes in variation in permeability and thickness of the crushed zone. Comparing the data to the analytical model, only a reasonable deviation is observable which is probably resulting from assumptions for analytically solving the diffusion equation. It was demonstrated that the mismatch between observed experimental results and model prediction does not result in shortcomings of the analytic solution.

Furthermore, the influence of the storage capacity of the upstream volume was discussed and turned out as a potential major source of error. It was shown that justifiable changes in storage capacity lead to drastic flow corrections producing results consistent with the analytical model.

The application of the pore-flow as well as the pore-pressure method on perforated rock samples requires further investigations. When performing the pore-pressure method, an improved signal-to-noise ratio may enlarge the maximal detectable frequency. An investigation of the frequency dependence of diffusivity and permeability can be realized by performing a set of smaller frequencies. Therefore, the recording time needs to be increased. For the pore-flow method, a precise determination of the storage capacity of the entire upstream reservoir including the sample vessel and sealing is indispensable. The question of suitable frequencies for the

investigation of crushed zones using the pore-flow method remains unanswered. The numerical simulation suggests that the highest applied frequencies might suffice significantly depending on diffusivity of the crushed zone.

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Appendix A: Analytic solution

The equations based on the general solution of the Bessel differential equation with applied boundary conditions, equations (2.31) to (2.34):

$$\begin{aligned}
 -A_1 K_{1(\eta_1 r_i)} + B_1 I_{1(\eta_1 r_i)} &= -\frac{q\mu}{k_1 \eta_1} \\
 A_1 K_{0(\eta_1 r_b)} + B_1 I_{0(\eta_1 r_b)} &= A_2 K_{0(\eta_2 r_c)} + B_2 I_{0(\eta_2 r_c)} \\
 \frac{k_1 \eta_1}{\mu} A_1 K_{1(\eta_1 r_b)} - \frac{k_1 \eta_1}{\mu} B_1 I_{1(\eta_1 r_b)} &= \frac{k_2 \eta_2}{\mu} A_2 K_{1(\eta_2 r_c)} - \frac{k_2 \eta_2}{\mu} B_2 I_{1(\eta_2 r_c)} \\
 \frac{k_2 \eta_2}{\mu} A_2 K_{1(\eta_2 r_d)} - \frac{k_2 \eta_2}{\mu} B_2 I_{1(\eta_2 r_d)} &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

were simplified to enable an easier calculation of coefficients A_1 and B_1

$$-A_1 a + B_1 b - \alpha = 0 \quad (5.1)$$

$$A_1 c + B_1 d - A_2 e - B_2 f = 0 \quad (5.2)$$

$$A_1 g - B_1 h - A_2 i + B_2 j = 0 \quad (5.3)$$

$$A_2 k - B_2 l = 0 \quad (5.4)$$

Solving the system of equations, the required coefficients read like:

$$A_1 = \left(\frac{\frac{h\alpha}{b} + \frac{id\alpha}{be + \frac{bfk}{l}} - \frac{jkda}{ble + bfk}}{\frac{ic}{e + \frac{fk}{l}} - \frac{bjc}{le + fk} + \frac{ida}{be + \frac{bfk}{l}} - \frac{jkda}{ble + bfk} - g + \frac{ha}{b}} \right) \quad (5.5)$$

$$B_1 = \left(\frac{\frac{ah\alpha}{b} + \frac{aid\alpha}{be + \frac{bfk}{l}} - \frac{ajkda}{ble + bfk}}{\frac{bic}{e + \frac{fk}{l}} - \frac{bjc}{le + fk} + \frac{ida}{e + \frac{fk}{l}} - \frac{jkda}{le + fk} - bg + ha} \right) - \frac{\alpha}{b} \quad (5.6)$$

Appendix B: Results

Pore-pressure analysis

Table 5.1: Pore-pressure analysis: Phase shift and amplitude ratio determined from sample 1: Berea sandstone.

Frequency	Phase shift	Uncertainty of phase shift	Amplitude ratio	Uncertainty of amplitude ratio
(Hz)	(cycles)	(cycles)	(-)	(-)
0.1	0.21	0.02	0.34	0.05
0.2	0.26	0.02	0.18	0.02
0.3	0.27	0.02	0.12	0.02
0.5	0.32	0.05	0.06	0.03
1.0	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.2
1.5	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.3

Table 5.2: Pore-pressure analysis: Phase shift and amplitude ratio determined from sample 2: Roter Main sandstone.

Frequency	Phase shift	Uncertainty of phase shift	Amplitude ratio	Uncertainty of amplitude ratio
(Hz)	(cycles)	(cycles)	(-)	(-)
0.05	-	-	-	-
0.1	0.260	0.002	0.136	0.002
0.2	0.31	0.02	0.066	0.007
0.3	0.35	0.01	0.051	0.006
0.5	0.2	0.1	0.032	0.007
1.0	0.6	0.3	0.08	0.04

Table 5.3: Pore-pressure analysis: Hydraulic Parameters determined from sample 1: Berea sandstone.

Frequency	Diffusivity	Storativity	Transmissivity	Permeability	Specific storage capacity
(Hz)	(m^2/s)	(-)	(m^2/s)	(m^2)	(P^{-1})
0.1	0.295	$7.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-9}$
0.2	0.172	$6.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.8 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-9}$
0.3	0.169	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.7 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$8.4 \cdot 10^{-10}$
0.5	0.070	$5.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-9}$
1.0	-	-	-	-	-
1.5	-	-	-	-	-

Table 5.4: Pore-pressure analysis: Hydraulic Parameters determined from sample 2: Roter Main sandstone.

Frequency	Diffusivity	Storativity	Transmissivity	Permeability	Specific storage capacity
(Hz)	(m^2/s)	(-)	(m^2/s)	(m^2)	(P^{-1})
0.05	-	-	-	-	-
0.1	0.185	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$8.0 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$9.2 \cdot 10^{-10}$
0.2	0.085	$4.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3.9 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$9.9 \cdot 10^{-10}$
0.3	0.055	$6.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-9}$
0.5	-	-	-	-	-
1.0	-	-	-	-	-

Pore-flow analysis

Table 5.5: Pore-flow analysis: Phase shift and amplitude ratio determined from sample 1: Berea sandstone.

Frequency	Phase shift	Uncertainty of phase shift	Amplitude ratio	Uncertainty of amplitude ratio
(Hz)	(cycles)	(cycles)	($m^3/s/Pa$)	($m^3/s/Pa$)
0.1	0.218	0.005	$5.7 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-12}$
0.2	0.201	0.003	$5.0 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-12}$
0.3	0.161	0.002	$5.43 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$8 \cdot 10^{-13}$
0.5	0.246	0.004	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-12}$
1.0	0.135	0.004	$5.2 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-12}$
1.5	0.125	0.008	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-12}$

Table 5.6: Pore-flow analysis: Phase shift and amplitude ratio determined from sample 2: Roter Main sandstone.

Frequency	Phase shift	Uncertainty of phase shift	Amplitude ratio	Uncertainty of amplitude ratio
(Hz)	(cycles)	(cycles)	($m^3/s/Pa$)	($m^3/s/Pa$)
0.05	0.180	0.002	$5.62 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$7 \cdot 10^{-13}$
0.1	0.208	0.004	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-12}$
0.2	0.231	0.004	$4.4 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-12}$
0.3	0.242	0.001	$4.25 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-13}$
0.5	0.2	0.1	$4.02 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$7 \cdot 10^{-13}$
1.0	0.189	0.004	$3.8 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-12}$

Table 5.7: Pore-flow analysis: Phase shift and amplitude ratio determined from sample 3: Berea sandstone with alternative downstream configuration.

Frequency	Phase shift	Uncertainty of phase shift	Amplitude ratio	Uncertainty of amplitude ratio
(Hz)	(cycles)	(cycles)	($m^3/s/Pa$)	($m^3/s/Pa$)
0.05	0.230	0.005	$1.42 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$4 \cdot 10^{-12}$
0.1	0.1	0.3	$1.28 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-12}$
0.2	0.227	0.006	$9.8 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-12}$
0.3	0.224	0.008	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-12}$
0.5	-0.06	0.5	$4.9 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-12}$
1.0	0.15	0.01	$3.9 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-12}$
1.5	0.122	0.009	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-12}$
2.0	0.10	0.01	$4.9 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-12}$

Numerical simulation

Table 5.8: Numerical modelling: Phase shift and amplitude ratio determined from pressure and flow for a variation in crushed zone permeability. Three simulation series were performed with a permeability of 14, 15 and 16 m² of the crushed zone.

Frequency (Hz)	Phase shift (cycles)	Uncertainty of phase shift (cycles)	Amplitude ratio (m ³ /s/Pa)	Uncertainty of amplitude ratio (m ³ /s/Pa)
0.1	0.2293	1 · 10 ⁻⁴	8.937 · 10 ⁻¹³	7 · 10 ⁻¹⁶
0.5	0.1636	3 · 10 ⁻⁸	3.5967 · 10 ⁻¹²	4 · 10 ⁻¹⁹
1.0	0.1277	3 · 10 ⁻⁸	5.2161 · 10 ⁻¹²	1 · 10 ⁻¹⁸
1.5	0.1133	1 · 10 ⁻⁷	6.1927 · 10 ⁻¹²	3 · 10 ⁻¹⁸
0.1	0.1563	2 · 10 ⁻⁵	7.492 · 10 ⁻¹³	4 · 10 ⁻¹⁶
0.5	0.0506	1 · 10 ⁻⁸	1.2860 · 10 ⁻¹²	3 · 10 ⁻²⁰
1.0	0.0319	5 · 10 ⁻⁸	1.3499 · 10 ⁻¹²	6 · 10 ⁻¹⁹
1.5	0.0261	2 · 10 ⁻⁸	1.3840 · 10 ⁻¹²	9 · 10 ⁻²⁰
0.1	0.0275	3 · 10 ⁻⁴	1.481 · 10 ⁻¹³	3 · 10 ⁻¹⁶
0.5	0.0121	2 · 10 ⁻⁵	1.5033 · 10 ⁻¹³	1 · 10 ⁻¹⁹
1.0	0.0159	1 · 10 ⁻⁵	1.5151 · 10 ⁻¹³	4 · 10 ⁻¹⁸
1.5	0.0211	1 · 10 ⁻⁷	1.5309 · 10 ⁻¹³	1 · 10 ⁻¹⁹

Table 5.9: Numerical modelling: Phase shift and amplitude ratio determined from pressure and flow for a variation in thickness of the crushed zone. Four simulation series were performed with a thickness of 1, 5, 10 and 15 mm of the crushed zone.

Frequency (Hz)	Phase shift (cycles)	Uncertainty of phase shift (cycles)	Amplitude ratio (m ³ /s/Pa)	Uncertainty of amplitude ratio (m ³ /s/Pa)
0.1	0.2365	4 · 10 ⁻⁵	9.2092 · 10 ⁻¹³	8 · 10 ⁻¹⁷
0.5	0.1894	4 · 10 ⁻⁸	4.0364 · 10 ⁻¹²	7 · 10 ⁻¹⁹
1.0	0.1600	6 · 10 ⁻⁸	6.4213 · 10 ⁻¹²	3 · 10 ⁻¹⁸
1.5	0.1485	5 · 10 ⁻⁸	8.0433 · 10 ⁻¹²	2 · 10 ⁻¹⁸
0.1	0.2293	1 · 10 ⁻⁴	8.937 · 10 ⁻¹³	7 · 10 ⁻¹⁶
0.5	0.1636	3 · 10 ⁻⁸	3.5967 · 10 ⁻¹²	4 · 10 ⁻¹⁹
1.0	0.1277	3 · 10 ⁻⁸	5.2161 · 10 ⁻¹²	1 · 10 ⁻¹⁸
1.5	0.1133	1 · 10 ⁻⁷	6.1927 · 10 ⁻¹²	3 · 10 ⁻¹⁸
0.1	0.2233	1 · 10 ⁻⁴	8.872 · 10 ⁻¹³	8 · 10 ⁻¹⁶
0.5	0.1449	4 · 10 ⁻⁸	3.3045 · 10 ⁻¹²	5 · 10 ⁻¹⁹
1.0	0.1075	7 · 10 ⁻⁸	4.4736 · 10 ⁻¹²	3 · 10 ⁻¹⁸
1.5	0.0930	1 · 10 ⁻⁷	5.1243 · 10 ⁻¹²	3 · 10 ⁻¹⁸
0.1	0.2194	2 · 10 ⁻⁴	8.824 · 10 ⁻¹³	7 · 10 ⁻¹⁶
0.5	0.1332	2 · 10 ⁻⁸	3.0796 · 10 ⁻¹²	1 · 10 ⁻¹⁹
1.0	0.0965	1 · 10 ⁻⁷	3.9997 · 10 ⁻¹²	3 · 10 ⁻¹⁸
1.5	0.0827	6 · 10 ⁻⁸	4.4946 · 10 ⁻¹²	8 · 10 ⁻¹⁹